

1 Zic3 is the major imprinting factor active in the TE commitment processes.

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6 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
7 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here discovery of Zic3
8 as a lineage commitment factor or lineage commitment cooperating factor in embryonic stem cells of the
9 human embryo. Zic3 was the major imprinting factor active in the TE commitment processes, where it
10 functioned with histone methyltransferase KMT2E.

11 Citations

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